

ISic3045

I.Sicily inscription 3045

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo / Pulera)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334358

1. Ὀλύμπιος.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645399

PHI 334358

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 41.0800

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Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M. 1991. Meligunìs Lipára V. Scavi nella necropoli
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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3045. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388027>